

D6.1: Scale-up success factors and targeted EU regions

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Lost and Waste
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FEBA	European Food Banks Federation
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
MSI	Management Systems International
NRI	Near Infra-Red
PTA	Problem Tree Analysis
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
WPs	Work Packages

Executive summary

Through stakeholder workshops, critical success factors for scaling the nine ZeroW systemic solutions to FLW) were identified. Primarily, finding with suitable **business models** for the SILL solutions and aligning operational costs with implementation costs constitute prerequisites for uptake. This necessitates an economic assessment that all SILLs must undertake. Similarly, **legislation** (either at EU or regional level) influences the scalability of the solutions, in some cases needing adjustments in specific policy domains (notably in SILLs 4 and 8). Furthermore, In SILLs 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 9, datasets form a crucial part of the solution. Both **technological infrastructures and data governance models** need to be established to ensure sustained engagement and capabilities from both data owners and recipients to leverage the platforms' services. Moreover, for many tools, such as those created in SILLs 9, 3, 5, and 6, validating the **usefulness and/or user convenience** of the solutions among end-users is an important next step, so that required changes (e.g., in product or strategy) can be imposed timely. On the longer term, for many solutions (especially SILLs 2, 3, 5, and 6), replication is a promising scaling strategy, emphasising the need to **transfer** the solutions to other sectors or applications. Accordingly, **collaboration** across food supply chain actors would enhance those solutions' scaling processes.

1. Introduction

ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZeroW approach

To reach its goals, ZeroW is divided into 11 Work Packages (WPs) with different goals, tasks and deliverables. The current deliverable is part of WP6, which aims to foster the systemic innovations that are built in the SILLs, by building capacities towards near-zero Food Loss and Waste (FLW). Importantly, WP6 aims to support T4.3 by organising concrete workshops and other types of activities, which help to (1) identify and (2) address what is needed for increasing the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) of the SILLs' solutions. This link between WP6 and WP4 is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 WP6 tasks, deliverables, objectives, and link with other WPs

Mapping ZeroW outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, and against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.1. Scale up success factors and targeted EU regions	Will define critical success factors for innovation scale-up and identify high-potential EU regions.	Chapters 3, 4, 5	Chapter 3 describes the methodology. Chapter 4 presents, per SILL solution, the enablers, barriers and differences across EU regions to be considered when scaling-up the FLW solutions. Chapter 5 provides a general overview of recurring success factors for innovation scale-up.
TASKS			
T6.1. Innovation scale-up success factors and incentives in targeted EU regions	Based on stakeholder analysis, relevant actors will be invited in Stakeholder Workshops in the three macro regions represented in the project (Northern, South-West and South-East/Central Europe). The ZeroW SILLs will be presented (focus on credibility, relevance and observability with input from WP4 and WP5), and their innovation potential will be analysed (using the SIRL) at the level of the corresponding NUTS2 ¹ regions. NUTS2 regions with high scale-up potential will be identified and critical success factors and required scale up incentives will be determined.	Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5	Chapters 2 and 3 describe the preparations and methodologies for the stakeholder workshops. Chapters 4 and 5 present the success factors, enablers, barriers and regional differences that were identified by the stakeholders during the interactive workshops.

¹ NUTS 2: basic regions for the application of regional policies.

Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

- Chapter 1 provides introduction to the document objectives and structure.
- Chapter 2 situates the role of the stakeholder workshops in the ZeroW project and describes the actions in preparation for the workshops, including how the SILLs were grouped in a meaningful way (i.e., similar stakeholders relevant to discuss their FLW solutions) to organise the workshops across the three predefined macro-regions. The preparatory activities that were conducted as part of a sound preparatory course for the stakeholder workshops were:
 - (1) the SIRL baseline measurement;
 - (2) the 1-on-1 meetings between the WP6 lead and the SILLs to explore their scale-up ambitions;
 - (3) grouping of the SILLs for mutual workshops wherein maximal use of synergies is materialised (in terms of stakeholder participants and discussion content) based on a matchmaking performed by WP6;
 - (4) problem tree analyses (PTA) to fine-tune the presentation of the SILL solution to stakeholders as key solutions to particular FLW problems.
- Chapter 3 presents the workshop approach and provides practical and organisational guidance for the workshops' organisation.
- Chapter 4 presents the results of the problem tree exercises as well as the critical success factors and regional differences obtained from the workshop. These inputs are grouped per workshop and presented per SILL solution.
- Chapter 5 summarizes the main recurring success factors for innovation scale-up, and the most critical differences across EU regions to take into account when scaling FLW solutions.

2. Preparatory activities conducted between M12-M18

2.1. SIRL baseline round

Research and development innovations often focus on a new technology, whereby the technological readiness level scaling is a very well-known tool to evaluate the innovation's readiness to be scaled. Within the ZeroW project, we start from the idea that innovations with high scale-up potential are never 'isolated' innovations, but rather a portfolio of different complementary innovations that address various dimensions (Sartas et al., 2020). For the ZeroW SILL innovations, this implies that the SILLs identify and develop innovations in every innovation dimension that is relevant for their solution to be scaled up. To ensure such a systemic approach, an evaluation tool, the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level assessment (SIRL), was developed within T4.1 of WP4. The tool can be consulted in chapter 5 of *D4.1 Systemic innovation gaps*. The SIRL tool aims to support SILLs to (1) identify all innovation dimensions that are relevant for their solution building and (2) evaluate not only the technological readiness of their solution, but the full readiness of their solution, by assessing the readiness per innovation dimension. The SIRL tool is inspired by the work of Sartas et al. (2020).

Between September 2022 and January 2023, each SILL used the SIRL tool in an internal SILL workshop. The SILL partners together identified the dimensions to be considered for their complete solution building. Generally, the five generic dimensions that could be relevant are technology, behavioural change processes, business operations and strategies, the policy framework, and the value chain conditions and relations. Once these dimensions were identified, they were described in the context of the SILL innovation at hand. Next, the SILLs assessed the current level of their innovative solution for each of the identified dimensions. They also described what a fully implemented and tested innovation would look like for their specific solution, i.e., readiness level 9.

It is important to note that it is often not possible to reach level 9 within the timeframe of the ZeroW project. Therefore, the SILLs also indicated the level they aim to achieve during the project lifetime. Nevertheless, formulating what level 9 means for each dimension allows to concretise where you want to land with the innovation, and helps to formulate the next steps needed to get there.

Thereafter, they described the intermediate steps and consecutive actions needed to move from the current level to the target and final level. In a final step, the SILLs could

link these descriptions to the readiness level scales available in literature and assign numbers to each step. The SILLs reported the results of this exercise in reports that will be published in D5.2 on month 26 (first internal version), month 38 (second internal version) and month 46 (final version).

The use of the SIRL tool will be continued throughout the project. The SILLs need to regularly follow-up the intermediate steps to proceed on the readiness ladder for each dimension. A recapitulation (and re-adjustment, if necessary) of how to get from their current level to the target level needs to be performed regularly. The definition of the different readiness levels for each dimension is based on the available readiness level scales in literature or can be tailored to the needs of a specific SILL. For more details on these scales, we refer to D4.1 Systemic innovation gaps. As a point of reference, please see figure 4 in D4.1 for the description of readiness levels 1 to 9 for the technical dimension.

The visual outcome of the SIRL exercise is a radar graph for each SILL that presents its relevant dimensions (on the diagonal axes) and clearly shows which dimensions are least developed compared to their target level (the further from the centre, the more developed). Annex III shows these radar graphs for all 9 SILLs. When comparing the SIRL results, it is clear that each of the SILLs has different types of dimensions to focus on and consequently different bottleneck dimensions. These bottleneck dimensions are used to determine the focus of each of the T6.1 workshops, by matching the SILLs into four clusters, as will be explained in detail hereafter.

2.2. 1-on-1 meetings to explore the SILLs' scaling ambitions

The goal of the regional stakeholder workshops in T6.1 is to identify critical success factors for scaling-up the FLW innovations and we presume that putting focus on the bottleneck dimensions is important for this. At the start of T6.1, the task lead and WP6 partners agreed that the first step would be to explore the SILL's scaling ambitions. We distinguished between three types of scaling; expansion, replication and collaboration, as described by Management Systems International (MSI et al. 2016)².

² Management Systems International [MSI] et al. (2016) distinguishes 3 categories of scaling based on the degree to which the organization that managed the initial prototype or project continues to control the scaling. The first category is expansion and refers to increasing the scope of operations of the organization that originally developed the project. Replication involves another party to execute the scaling, but this adopting organisation remains at arms-length of the originating organisation. The third type of scaling is collaboration and can be situated between expansion and replication.

Based on these ambitions and the results of the SIRL baseline exercise (described above), WP6 grouped the SILLs for joint workshops.

In order to prepare the stakeholder workshops and group the 9 SILLs in small groups for mutual workshops (1 workshop in each of the 3 macro-regions represented in the project), WP6 sent out a questionnaire (see annex IV) to all SILL coordinators. They were asked to discuss these questions with their SILL partners and an online meeting was scheduled with each SILL to discuss their answers to these questions. Table 4 shows the schedule of the online meetings and the links to the respective meeting materials.

In what follows, we report on the key points raised during these exploratory meetings wherein WP6 tried to get a better insight into the SILLs' ambitions regarding scale-up.

Meeting minutes in the form of completed questionnaires are available in this Excel overview: [Questions for SILLs 1to1 meetings.xlsx \(sharepoint.com\)](#)³

³ The link is included for the benefit of the ZeroW Consortium members, using this document as input for their work. This link is not freely accessible

Table 3 Overview of 1-on-1 meetings

Date	SILL	Attendees	Link to meeting recording⁴
13/03/2023	SILL1	Andra Tanase, Sasa Straus, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Kata Trifkovic, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
13/03/2023	SILL8	Guilherme Gonçalves, Helena Cardoso, Pedro Miguel Macedo Geda, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Kata Trifkovic, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
15/03/2023	SILL2	Leticia Requena, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Kata Trifkovic, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
15/03/2023	SILL5	Jose Luis Gallego Álvarez, Felix Gomez, Victor Ortiz, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Kata Trifkovic, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
15/03/2023	SILL4	Bart Van Droogenbroeck, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Lisa Van den Bossche, Kata Trifkovic, Etienne Rubens, An Braekevelt, Anna Twarogowska, Mikayel Hovhannisyan, Milena Zdravkovic	meeting recording
16/03/2023	SILL7	Renzo Akkerman, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Lisa Van den Bossche, Kata Trifkovic	Meeting recording
21/03/2023	SILL3	Martynas Velička, Justė Vežikauskaitė, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
21/03/2023	SILL 9	Joris Wagenaar, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording
23/03/2023	SILL 6	Roberto Moran, Asincar, Isabeau Coopmans, Anna George, Lisa Van den Bossche	meeting recording

⁴ The links to the recordings are included for the benefit of the ZeroW Consortium members, using this document as input for their work. Those links are not freely accessible.

2.2.1. SILL 1 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 1 aims to build a FLW data sharing platform. For this, they collaborate with local and national authorities. Their main challenges are to build awareness and trust amongst possible data platform users. SILL 1 is developed in parallel in two countries, Slovenia and Romania, but will bring these two solutions together to form a total solution that can be replicable anywhere, starting from different kinds of input data. With the support of a local municipality (Pomurje, Slovenia) food production data is automatically collected and this is used to calculate FLW. In Romania, FLW data are based on an estimation.

SILL 1 mainly wants to focus on expanding its operations, growing the platform. The stakeholders that are needed for this are, amongst others, public bodies, farmers, food related business associations. SILL 1 is in contact with these actors. From within the ZeroW project, SILL 1 could benefit most from participation from WP3, EV ILVO and TNO for the development of the data space and the connectors. Furthermore, they indicated that SILL 5 will collect a lot of data via their multi-sensor platform, which could be interesting to share via SILL 1.

2.2.2. SILL 2 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 2 is developing a new innovative packaging that communicates the actual shelf life of a product, in this case fish. This is achieved via a special ink that changes colour depending on the freshness of the fish. An app will be developed to support retail staff, and in a later stage to support consumers.

Overall, this SILL is developed in a very balanced way on all dimensions. The dimension that was considered most challenging is the behavioural dimension, which implies changing the behaviour of consumers and retail staff so that they know how to use this information and trust it. Retailers can provide access to information regarding consumer behaviour and are thus very relevant stakeholders.

SILL 2 would like to explore to what extent other retailers could benefit from the solution they are developing and thus SILL 8 would be a good match. SILL 5 could also be relevant for the development of the shelf-life prediction app, and WP8 could support in the policy dimension, where SILL 2 aims to reach readiness level 7.

2.2.3. SILL 3 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 3 will compare different computer vision methods to reduce the food waste in tomato production that is linked to ineffective yield planning and the production of 'ugly' tomatoes. Their solution will determine the tomato ripeness and use this input to optimise the entire tomato supply chain.

They want to demonstrate the usefulness of their solution to potential end users across Europe and connect with agro-technology providers who could bring the solution to the market. This will support the development of the business dimension of their innovation. The solution developed by SILL 3 could be expanded to bell-peppers and cucumbers, but in this phase, it would be most relevant to focus on regions that have a lot of tomato growers, such as Italy and Spain.

2.2.4. SILL 4 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 4 aims to reduce the loss and waste of fruits and vegetables that are currently not marketed due to supply and demand mismatching, quality or cosmetic standards that are not reached or unsold fruits and vegetables from retailers. This will be done by implementing a mobile processing unit that uses innovative techniques and allows the production of high-level end-products. Rebalancing this supply and demand will also ensure a steady supply of healthy food (juices made from the leftover fruits and vegetables) to the foodbanks to ensure food security.

A first application of this mobile fruit and vegetable processing unit will be at an auction to process unsold feedstock. Part of the production will go to the local foodbank, who would normally receive these goods in donations, but is not able to distribute them all at once. The regulatory and legal dimension is important to ensure the right incentives for all involved parties. The main challenge for SILL 4 is the business and value chain dimensions. How can this be integrated in the collaboration of food banks and auctions? What is the business model for the auctions? Interaction with other foodbanks, auctions, retailers and policy makers are important for the stakeholder workshops.

SILL 4 would benefit from knowledge exchanges with SILL7, since the latter is working on aligning surplus food donations with needs from food banks following food charity demand.

2.2.5. SILL 5 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 5 aims to use a multispectral classification platform to assess shelf-life and quality aspects early in the supply chain and in an automated manner. This pre-sorting will take place in the pre-processing and retail phases of the supply chain and will allow process optimisation resulting in FLW reduction.

The main barriers for SILL 5 are on the one hand to train staff to use these technologies and interpret the results (behavioural dimension), and on the other hand, to develop a profitable business model. It is not clear if Multiscan will be bringing this to market themselves or via agro-tech providers. Feedback from other tomato traders and retailers would be very relevant to develop the business model.

SILL 5 would benefit most from collaboration with SILL 2, SILL 3 and SILL 6. All these SILLs use a similar technology and both SILL 3 and 6 aim to bring their solution to market via an agro-tech solution provider.

2.2.6. SILL 6 input from the questionnaire and meeting

In SILL 6, the focus is on optimising the control and optimisation processes of minced meat production. A lot of food is wasted due to the current lack of integration of these processes and the invasive technologies applied. SILL 6 will use a portable Near Infrared Spectroscopy solution to allow constant monitoring that is non-invasive. This solution will be brought to the market via technology providers such as Hispatec; it would be relevant to invite such players to the workshop.

A main challenge for SILL 6 is the integration of their solution in the meat producers' production processes. It would be relevant to exchange experience on this topic with SILL 5. The technological dimension is well developed; nevertheless, interaction with SILL 3, who is using the same technology, would be relevant.

2.2.7. SILL 7 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 7 is developing different tools to support foodbanks to reduce their internal food waste and increase the amount of food that they can redistribute:

- Supply and demand prediction tools to forecast the expected number of food bank customers, as well as FSC management and optimisation to predict the supply. These tools will use big data analytics;
- Handbook of food waste reduction strategies available for food banks;
- Decision support tool for waste reduction initiatives at food banks;
- Donation tool for donors on products that are ready for donation.

For SILL 7, it was emphasised that these tools are not necessarily interdependent, so separate scale-up is possible. The sustainable maintenance of the tools must be investigated, as there is no strategy yet. Regarding how to finance scaling, a software company could sell these tools to food banks; however, public funding should be explored. Again, the difference between the individual tools (listed above) was emphasised, e.g., for the donation support tool, supermarkets might be willing to pay for this. As the main scaling ambition, they would like to replicate to other food banks, via the European Food Banks Federation (FEBA). Collaboration with FEBA is therefore crucial.

The SILL would like to invite SILL 8's partner SONAE to their workshop. As a retailer, they could provide input on the donation tool. Another key invitee are food banks in other countries, particularly Germany, the Netherlands, and Lithuania.

2.2.8. SILL 8 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 8 aims to develop special containers to pre-processed food that is no longer fit for human consumption and would normally go to landfill, biogas or animal feed. If processed correctly, it could serve as a medium to produce micro-algae that are useful for the production of cosmetics or bioplastics.

The SIRL exercise clearly showed that the technological dimension has been most strongly developed, while the behavioural, policy, business and supply chain dimensions require more attention. SILL 8 would like to interact with policy makers, WP8 and SILL 2 to understand better the legal limitations that exist today and how these could be overcome. Other relevant participants to the workshop are micro-algae producers, other retailers and packaging suppliers. In table 5, all the relevant actions for SILL 8 to take are listed per dimension.

3.2.9. SILL 9 input from the questionnaire and meeting

SILL 9 can only be replicated in countries that have food waste data on consumer level in order to build their solutions (app; label, recipes). They also indicated that the solutions would work best in regions that have already done similar research or awareness campaigns. SILL 9 envisions local governments, NGOs or supermarkets as potential scaling-up partners. SILL 1 is in close contact with all these types of partners and has data available. It would thus be a suitable candidate for exploring the scale-up potential of SILL 9.

2.3. Matchmaking of SILLs into 4 groups

Based on the above information obtained from the 1-on-1 meetings with the SILLs, wherein a better view of their scaling ambitions and stakeholders relevant to target for kick-starting this type of scaling was obtained, the SILLs were matched for joint workshops. We grouped SILLs based on similarities or complementarity in targeted stakeholders, technology, route to market and SIRL dimensions that require development. This resulted in 4 matches: 3 groups of 2 SILLs and one group of 3 SILLs, as presented hereafter.

Workshop 1: SILL1 & SILL9

Slovenia would be an interesting region for SILL 9 since data on food waste at a consumer level is being collected there. SILL 1 has local partners and stakeholders that are relevant for SILL 9. The presence of a data platform could be considered as a prerequisite for SILL 9 to develop their solutions.

SILL 1 needs to build awareness and trust; showcasing what can be done with the data collected (in another region) could be a way of doing so.

SILL 1 and SILL 9 are both faced with the challenge of how to operationalise FLW, in kg CO2 equivalents, in nutritional value of the food being wasted or simply in kg of food.

	SILL 1 (Romania, Slovenia)	SILL 9 (The Netherlands)
Where	Anywhere, profile close to Slovenia/Romania	Country which has FW data on consumer level
Who	Food system actors, public bodies, farmer, business associations WP 3, ILVO, TNO, SILL 5	Local governments, NGOs, supermarkets, GS1, existing apps
What	Awareness building, trust building: convince data owners to share their data (by showcasing possible applications)	Find parties that want to develop this innovation into a working business model

Figure 4 Matchmaking of group 1

Workshop 2: SILL4 & SILL7

SILL 4 is developing a solution to process excess fruit and vegetables in a product with a longer shelf life. This could be very relevant for the Food banks who often receive fresh fruits and vegetables on peak moments and are not able to distribute them all. So, SILL 4 is one way for food banks to optimise their way of working (aim of SILL 7). SILL 4 wants to share its solution with as many food banks as possible, and this could be done via SILL 7.

	SILL 4 (Belgium)	SILL 7 (The Netherlands)
Where	-Any region that has a surplus of different fruit & vegetables year round (to ensure varied end products). -Support of tech providers in the region -Link to social economy in the region	-Anywhere, even outside Europe
Who	-Feedstocks suppliers (growers, auctions) -Technology providers -Potential customers -Investors -agrifood service providers -fruit & veg processing companies	-foodbanks/organisations that redistribute food -retailers (donating companies) -ING -Why Waste, Toogoodtogo -SILL 8 & 4
What	-Network analysis to identify exploitation potential of the mobile unit -Evaluate economic feasibility -Business plan development	-Identify other foodbanks/organisations that want to replicate our solutions -discuss funding of the maintenance of the solutions

Figure 5 Matchmaking of group 2

Workshop 3: SILL2 & SILL8

SILL 2 has connections with a packaging manufacturer (Termoformas) – they could potentially be an end user of the micro-algae that are the end product of SILL 8.

SILL 2 would like to interact with other retailers to assess their requirements in implementing smart packaging. SILL 8 has a retail partner, Sonae.

The solution developed by SILL 8 would be easier to implement if the packaging were biodegradable (e.g. SILL 2's new solution).

Other SILLs to invite: SILL 5. Both SILL 2 and SILL 5 need to develop an app to estimate remaining shelf life.

	SILL 2 (Spain, Valencia)	SILL 8 (Portugal)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable to all kinds of food stuffs, but most easy to replicate for another fish producer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Europe - Region where micro algae producers are present
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Retailers, Fish producers, packaging manufacturers (thermoformas), printers, all actors in the chain - Sisters project - SILL 2 app could provide input for SILL 8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy makers and legal experts - Bioplastic packaging & cosmetic industry - Other waste collectors eg foodbanks (other retailers) - Microalgae producers
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate potential of the new packaging for other retailers/fish suppliers (SILL 8 is led by Sonae) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determine economic viability - Are customers interested? - Legal limitations - Map Biomass characteristics & compare to needs of customers

Figure 6 Matchmaking of group 3

Workshop 4: SILL3 & SILL5 & SILL6

All SILLs are using the same technology (at least partly) which is near infra-red (NIR) spectroscopy and allows to evaluate a lot of parameters quite fast, without having to cut into the food. A technological exchange of experience could be relevant for all three SILLs.

SILL 3 and 6 do not plan on selling directly to the end users but to work via agro-tech service providers. For SILL 5 this is not clear. It could be interesting to involve these service providers and understand their requirements and way of working (= success factors).

SILL 5 and SILL 6 also have an impact on internal processes that need to be changed. Aldelis and Grupo La Cana could exchange experience on this.

	SILL 3 (Lithuania)	SILL 5 (Spain, Andalucia)	SILL 6 (Spain, Asturias)
Where	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anywhere in Europe - Most easy to replicate with similar vegetables (bell peppers, cucumbers) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tomato producing Regions (Spain, Netherlands, Italy, France) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anywhere, most contacts in Asturias
Who	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large and mid-scale greenhouse farmers or farmer associations & auctions - Agro (tech) provider - NGOs - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tomato producers or wholesalers - Value chain partners - SILL 6: same technology - SILL 2: predicting shelf life - SILL 3: same technology & product focus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SILL 5 & SILL 3: same technology - Service provider (IT company?) - End users: meat companies
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requirements from agro-tech providers who bring this solution to market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the new machine performant? - How to adapt the processes at GLC and with VC partners? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requirements from service providers who bring this solution to market

Figure 7 Matchmaking of group 4

2.4. Problem Tree Analyses

2.4.1. What is a Problem Tree Analysis (PTA) and why do we use it for preparing the T6.1 stakeholder workshops?

A Problem Tree exercise is a visualisation technique that helps to fully understand a problem. It is best done in group to create a shared understanding of the problem at hand. It forms part of the SILL Toolkit developed in WP4; T4.1. We used it in preparation of the stakeholder workshops during an online session with as many SILL partners as possible. In this exercise, we wanted to focus on the problem they are trying to solve, break it down in manageable chunks and separating the problem and its causes. By connecting the causes and the effects we come to new opportunities. The output of this exercise was used to structure the SILLs' presentation to the external stakeholders, and discussed in chapter 4.

3. Stakeholder workshops for identifying scale-up success factors

3.1 Stakeholder workshops: why?

WP6 aims to foster systemic innovation and scaling up of the SILLs' FLW solutions. In order to increase the systemic innovation readiness of the SILLs' solutions, it is relevant to gather and exploit inputs from external expert stakeholders at different stages of the project. The workshops organised in the framework of T6.1 are a first opportunity to present the SIRL results from the baseline measurement (provided by the SILLs at the end of 2022) to stakeholders, which will comment on them and validate them. Moreover, the purpose of the workshops is to gather inputs from relevant stakeholders concerning the requirements and conditions to mature SILLs solutions towards successful scaling up. This chapter explains the preparations and methods that will be used for these T6.1 stakeholder workshops.

3.2. Workshop practicalities: who, where, when?

Table 6 presents an overview of the groups and T6.1 workshops organised. Relevant local stakeholders were invited to the workshops, based on the bottleneck dimensions identified in the SIRL evaluation. In chapter 4, this general workshop information is provided in detail for each workshop.

Table 4 Overview of T6.1 workshops

Group	SILLs	Location	Date
Group 1	SILL 1 & SILL 9	online	24/11/2023
Group 2	SILL 4 & SILL 7	Brussels	25/09/2023
Group 3	SILL 2 & SILL 8	Valencia	19/10/2023
Group 4	SILL 5, SILL 3, SILL 6	Granada	24 & 25/10/2023

3.3. How? A participatory and interactive approach to identify scale-up success factors and incentives

Each workshop consists of 2 to 3 half days, whereby the same sessions and exercises are repeated per SILL solution. In other words, all participants take part in the same interactive exercise twice, each time focussing on another SILL. As such, invitees from both SILLs provide inputs to both SILLs. This generated synergies across SILLs and it was the reason for the careful organisation of the matchmaking between SILLs, as explained in chapter 3 of this deliverable.

The workshops started with a welcome, introduction of the goal of the exercises by WP6, and a getting to know each other moment.

Each SILL session (half a day per SILL) then consists of the following sub-sessions:

1. a general presentation of the SILL solution, focusing on a clear problem statement, followed by the explanation of the innovative solution and finally the status and ambition regarding scaling-up using the SILL tool baseline measurement. This sub-session ends with a selection of two (bottleneck) dimensions;
2. a demonstration of the SILL solution (if possible);
3. an interactive session, wherein input from the stakeholders is gathered on what they think are important trends that may influence the ability to book progress on the scaling ladders, focussing on two (bottleneck) dimensions as chosen by the group at the end of part (1). For this exercise, the group splits into two groups with each their own moderator to allow all participants sufficient time to explain their views. Both groups do the same exercise for both dimensions (this is important for validation). First, participants get ten minutes to write the trends/actions/events which they think can influence the scaling potential for that particular dimension in a positive or negative way. For positive influences (things that foster progression on the innovation scale), they are asked to use a green post-it, while for negative influences, they use a red post-it. After participants put their post-its on the whiteboard, the moderator reads them and categorises them. Second, the moderator facilitates a group discussion, to clarify what was meant with the input on the post-its and whether the group agrees. When the group comes to a consensus on the most important actions/trends/events (some are conducive to scaling, others hindering), the moderator asks the group to situate these actions/trends/events according to the urgency and importance for the SILL to address;
4. a plenary session wherein the results from the different groups are compared. The major threads and opportunities are summarised. Finally, the group is asked to reflect on how the obstacles could be overcome or the opportunities fostered.

Annex II presents the detailed script (playbook) for the workshops.

Note that not all the relevant dimensions are discussed during one workshop. This means that the list of enabling factors and barriers is not exhaustive. It is intended to help the SILLs to make progress in their bottleneck dimensions, not necessarily in all dimensions.

4. Results

4.1. Workshop on SILL 1 and SILL 9

4.1.1. General workshop information

The stakeholder workshop for SILLs 1 and 9 was organised online on the 24th of November 2023. A total of 31 participants joined the 3-hour workshop. The format of the workshop was adapted to an online setting (see the detailed agenda in annex V). Participants represented local and national policy makers, food processing companies, farmers, international non-profit organisations, knowledge centres on food related topics, project partners and the SILL 1 and 9 partners.

4.1.2. Problem tree exercise SILL 1

The problem that SILL 1 addresses is the lack of accurate and coherent data on FLW. This problem encompasses:

- Use of varied FLW definitions focusing on volumes and neglecting other aspects (nutritional value, GHG impact) important in designing effective reduction strategies for different stakeholders.
- Current FLW data are fragmented with a lot of missing data
- Inaccurate data collection processes (based primarily on subjective assessments) and a lack of standardized data collections methods.

Regional differences that emerged from the PTA workshop

- The more digitalised a region is (i.e., the more a region already has systems, habits, or governance implemented on food-related data collection and storage), the easier it will be to implement this solution because the automated data entry into the platform will be easier.
- There is a lack of knowledge on how digitalised regions are. Understanding different current realities in different regions is prerequisite to identifying promising region for scaling this solution.

4.1.3. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 1

The successful development and scaling-up of the FLW data platform relies on addressing four types of challenges, each encompassing several related critical success factors.

The first challenge revolves around establishing **uniform and shared procedures** across the food supply chain and EU regions for the **measurement of FLW generation**. Currently, the absence of sector-specific data collection procedures hampers an adequate collection and sharing of data, resulting in diverse approaches to both the type of data collected and the methodology employed. To address this, the data platform must allow for different ways of data entry. Also for potential replication in different settings, sectors and regions, the basic platform structure must be **flexible** and **adaptive**.

On the medium to long term, adopting **standardised methods** for expressing and reporting FLW quantities, such as an agreed and consistent choice of units. Also, a common understanding and shared ontology concerning FLW data management should be developed. This includes determining which key indicators the platform needs to include to support consequent decision-making in FLW data management, and what data helps to feed these indicators. To simplify and reduce the number of data entry methods, the solution would significantly benefit from **policy leadership in standardising data collection**, preferably at the EU level.

The platform providers should conduct regular and systematic **data quality checks**, while providing tailored feedback to data owners, enhancing data and platform trustworthiness.

The second challenge relates to **motivations of data owners and data recipients** to use the platform, also in the long-term. Intentions to use the data platform can only be formed after stakeholders are aware of the benefits of using this platform and they have incentives or willingness to use it. To start, the current co-existence of many different platforms and apps where FLW data can be reported should be addressed, preferably by moving towards **one or only few platforms** that combine all FLW data.

To improve trust in the data platform, information should largely flow in two directions, with a special attention to motivate data owners to share data by clarifying what they receive in return. The data platform providers play a crucial role in managing and coordinating this service and the **generation of added value**. For example, involving different types of stakeholders throughout the whole supply chain can create incentives for both data owners and data recipients.

For both sides, the platform should be user-friendly; this might require **adjustable interfaces** tailored to different target groups. FW data collection and manual entry generates additional bureaucracy, which may disincentivise stakeholders. The SILL

should therefore in the longer term seek how to mitigate this burden of **manual data entry**. The SILL will test an entirely automated and digitalised data collection process in the Pomurje region (Slovenia) as a use case based on an existing traceability system that tracks food throughout the supply chain from sowing until point of sales. Data collected includes sowing, harvesting date, storage capacities, yields, sold quantities etc.

The third challenge relates to **abilities**. To put the intention to use the data platform into action, data owners and recipients need to have the **skills and knowledge** to be able to use the platform successfully. One way to both motivate potential users and address their abilities is to organize **demonstrations** wherein users with different levels of skills can meet and be trained. Additionally, providing tailored **1-on-1 assistance** can enable the roll out of the platform.

The fourth challenge relates to addressing the access to **infrastructures** (e.g., mobile devices, wi-fi connection) and **resources** (e.g., time constraints) that potential users may lack, preventing them to be able to use the platform. To move from intentions to use the platform into sustainable usage, people need to have the **material and non-material resources (e.g., time, infrastructures)** allowing them to use the platform. Integrating a consistent use of the platform may require a change in operational working procedures and a shift towards more **data-driven** approaches. Particularly in technologically less developed regions, e.g., where people are not used to use technologies or digitalised methods, it will be more difficult to stimulate the use of a digital data gathering platform. Above, **automation** was highlighted as an enabler; however, it can also be a barrier if people are not used to automated solutions because then they might be reluctant to use the platform.

Furthermore, there is an **operational cost and an implementation cost** to using a data platform. Currently, the platform is free to use, but it is not yet clear if it will remain free in the future. The fact that the business model is not yet clear is a challenge for scaling up the project. Potential users will not be motivated to use a platform that is not guaranteed to continue to exist (for free) in the long run. To support opportunities, collaboration spaces (such as Policy Groups) as well as regional funding on this topic should be put in place.

4.1.4. Problem tree exercise SILL 9

Consumers often waste edible food while consuming unhealthy options due to factors like lack of knowledge, poor habits, and economic considerations. Overestimating quantities, impulse buying, and purchasing excess due to cheaper

large pack sizes contribute to this issue. Limited food management skills and unawareness of edible parts lead to inefficient ingredient use and food waste. A lack of understanding of personal decisions' impacts exacerbates the problem. Complications include the affordability of unhealthy foods and difficulties in balancing considerations when choosing amongst food products. SILL 9 introduces a menu planning tool and informative labels to guide optimal purchasing decisions, minimising greenhouse gas emissions and food waste while optimising nutritional value.

Regional differences that emerged from the PTA workshop

- The willingness to eat healthy/vegetarian is rising, but not in all EU regions.
- It will be easier to implement the app in regions/contexts where menu planning is more common. This is not a habit in all cultures/countries. This might also vary in urban versus rural areas.
- In some regions, vegetable gardens are popular and thus the menu planning should adapt to the yields, this is technically possible.
- The app needs to be adapted to popular local recipes.
- Availability of food waste data on consumer level is needed to adapt the label to a local situation.

4.1.6. Critical Success factors for scaling SILL 9

The long-term objective of SILL 9 is to shape consumers' purchasing habits by providing accurate sustainability information on food products. The label developed in SILL 9 will provide information on which food products generate less food waste and greenhouse gas emissions. This is in fact the first label that puts an emphasis on FLW while still optimising nutritional value. Nevertheless, changing behaviour requires more than just providing information. The menu planning app translates this information into action. In this way, SILL 9 aims to guide consumers to recipes that contain more sustainable ingredients. For SILL 9 to have impact at scale, it is important that as many consumers as possible use the label and meal planning app. The workshop participants provided input on how we could achieve this goal. Their suggestions can be clustered around stimulating consumer action on the one hand and how to address operational challenges on the other hand.

To boost **motivation**, the app could showcase potential monetary savings, leverage influencers for increased awareness and support meal planning during important family occasions, such as Christmas dinner. Moreover, children could be engaged through a tailored interface, fostering sustainable menu planning education. Other

ideas include a media campaign to launch the label and/or app in which we showcase users that have managed to reduce their food waste through using the label or app. Practical **usability** was also identified as essential. In reality, we see that meal planning is very dynamic, while the planning logic incorporated in the app will always be somewhat static. Future versions of the app should therefore ensure versatility, i.e., provide flexible menu planning to accommodate regional produce, allergies and dietary preferences, and allow adaptation of household composition and the manual entry of remaining fridge items.

It is also important to be aware of certain **external factors** that could challenge the usage of the app. A minimum of **culinary skills** is needed, which cannot be replaced by the app, but the latter will support their development. When people are under stress, they are less able to plan ahead and might have less **time** to use a menu planning app. Making the app as user-friendly as possible is a way to minimize opt-out due to a lack of time. Also, there is a large impact of the **food environment** which could overshadow the impact of the planning app. Government policies could step in here and influence the food environment. The underlying goal of such policies should be '*sludging*', i.e., making unsustainable food consumption decisions less attractive.

Participants did acknowledge that there are already many labels out there and that it is challenging to introduce a new label both towards consumers and on a regulatory level. There is a lot of new **EU legislation** being developed. The SILL partners do not know yet which impacts this will generate on the label. In any case, this pilot can be seen as a great opportunity to investigate what kind of labels work best and how the label can be linked to the meal planning app to provide all the info behind it.

On a consumer level, it is important to notice that **consumers** might not be interested in solutions that only target food waste reduction or greenhouse gas emissions. More importantly, they will not be interested in a label that is not used on all food products. To achieve this, the food industry needs to be actively involved. The same goes for retailers, who could adapt promotions to what is more sustainable. Retailers are of course reluctant to do so, and the food industry has not yet been involved. Other aspects related to consumers that are important to notice are that they might not know how to interpret the label correctly - training could mediate this issue. A risk that was mentioned is the rebound effect; when people make a sustainable choice in one product category, they might feel they have earned some credits to make a less sustainable choice in some other category.

Some **operational challenges** that were mentioned during the workshops include the fact that when the composition of the product changes, the label needs to be updated. This links to the fact that the label is static, while the actual impact of a product is variable over time. Data availability is also challenging, food waste data on

product level is needed to build the app in different regions. The data was collected in Wageningen and might not be representative for other cities.

4.2. Workshop on SILL 2 and SILL 8

4.2.1. General workshop information

A total of 20 participants joined the SILL 2 and SILL 8 workshop. These included SILL partners, project partners, packaging developers and technology developers. The workshop took place in Valencia, Spain on the 19th of October 2023.

4.2.2. Problem tree exercise SILL 2

SILL 2 deals with a substantial problem: food waste caused by people throwing away perfectly good food because they follow the date marking on the packaging. Even if the food is still safe to eat, they throw it away if it has passed the "use by" date. However, those dates are an estimate of the food safety, often including margins, hence not always presenting the actual state of the food product. On top of that, stores and distributors are also discarding unopened food packages that have passed use by dates. Not only the food goes to waste, but also the packaging. Currently, this packaging is not recycled but ends up in landfills. SILL 2 proposes a new **bio-based recyclable packaging** that is designed to keep the food fresh longer and includes a **smart label** that communicates the actual freshness of the product.

Regional differences that emerged from the workshop

- Participants mentioned that there are cross country differences with regards to habits, routines and (in)formal rules on waste management. This means that different type of dissemination strategies may be needed to support effective usage and deposition of the compostable packaging.
- Cross country differences with regards to **waste legislation**. Cross country differences in the EU on **legislation for packaging, recycling, and composting** will affect scalability in different regions and countries.

4.2.3. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 2

Throughout the workshop, several themes regarding the implementation of the new packaging and smart label at a large scale were discussed, with the primary aim of

mitigating FLW. Firstly, there was significant emphasis on designing the label in a manner that ensures **ease of interpretation** for all users. Secondly, discussions centred around the importance of ensuring the **transferability** of this packaging and label **to other food categories or online shopping**. Additionally, it was acknowledged that the implementation of this innovative packaging and labelling system may incur **higher costs** compared to traditional methods. Consequently, there was a pressing question on how to offset and cover these additional expenses effectively.

How to ensure the **ease of interpretation of the label for all users?** While utilising a mobile app for interpreting colour could be advantageous for some, it might pose challenges for others, particularly elderly individuals, colour blind people or those less comfortable with technology. Hence, it is crucial to distinguish different population groups needing varying levels of support due to differences in knowledge, abilities, and skills.

Accuracy and effective interpretation of the label were deemed paramount. This ensures that retailers can use the information to optimise stock control, while households can better determine product usage timelines. Gaining **consumer trust** in the product and packaging is essential for successful adoption, with an emphasis on making consumers feel empowered and in control. It will be important to measure and track how the label impacts consumers' decisions on whether to buy a food product based on the freshness indicator.

The label's ability to **indicate food safety and freshness** was deemed crucial, with consensus favouring a gradual colour change to represent freshness levels. There was also a recommendation for a **temporal** label indicating the current state of the food and the number of days the product will be edible. This will make it easier for retailers to organise mark-downs and for consumers to plan their weekly menus.

Concrete recommendations included improving interactive indicators to show freshness duration visually as well as linking label information to shopping list apps and self-scan devices. However, challenges such as resistance to behaviour change, consumer scepticism, and the need for knowledge and access to technology were acknowledged.

Participants highlighted the fact that more and more **shopping** is done **online**. This would mean that the interpretation of the shelf life of the products is not done by the consumer but by retail personnel. It will be important to have clear guidelines and communication on what colour corresponds to acceptable freshness.

An additional benefit of this new packaging is that it is **compostable**. A lack of knowledge surrounding compostable packaging disposal was mentioned as a barrier.

This can be altered by educating consumers but also through more policy alignment on waste disposal systems to make the system easier to understand.

For this solution to have impact at scale, it is important that it is **transferrable to different food products and shopping situations**. The technology that was used to develop this label is also applicable for other types of fish with minor adaptations. Further research will be needed to apply it for other food categories. The packaging design that maximises shelf life by separating the fluids from the fish will be easy to adapt for other fish. It will however require further research to develop this for other food categories.

Implementation of this innovative packaging and labelling system may incur **higher costs** compared to traditional methods. Consequently, there was a pressing question on how to convince packaging manufacturers and food companies to switch to this new packaging? **Legislative measures**, such as mandating compostable packaging across the EU, could drive successful adoption. Also, **cost-saving measures** can be pivotal in mitigating the initial investment burden. These could be achieved through leveraging the system's ability to provide more accurate and real-time data for all value chain partners, thereby facilitating informed decision-making and operational efficiency. A significant selling point lies in the system's capability to help **avoid recalls** and the consequential costs arising from perished products or cold chain interruptions. Unlike traditional date marking, the smart label can indicate spoilage, minimising financial losses and safeguarding brand reputation. Thus, retailers stand to benefit from potential cost reductions, particularly through longer-lasting food products. Despite potential logistical challenges, such as increased storage space requirements for diverse packaging options, the long-term advantages of reduced waste and enhanced product quality outweigh the initial complexities. Furthermore, aligning with legislation for compostable packaging presents an opportunity to reduce packaging waste sent to landfills, reducing disposal costs. However, clear indications must be provided to ensure correct disposal and maximise the benefits of compostable materials. The question was raised whether the label itself is also compostable or only the packaging. The implementation of innovative packaging and labelling systems offers various avenues for offsetting higher costs and **enhancing profitability**. Firstly, businesses can leverage the attractiveness of the packaging to charge higher fees to consumers, particularly by emphasising its high-tech features and ecological advantages. Positioning the system as a holistic solution and combining smart labels with compostable packaging enhances its appeal across the supply chain and aligns with sustainability initiatives.

In conclusion, **key selling points** include the system's ability to reduce food waste, avoid costly recalls, and minimise packaging waste sent to landfills. Furthermore, tapping into the growing importance of ecological considerations among consumers, particularly in markets like Spain, can drive adoption and market growth. Early adopters can benefit from a first-mover advantage, but careful consideration is required regarding the investment budget and internal alignment between sales, marketing, and supply chain departments. While compostable packaging and smart labels may be more expensive initially, potential cost reductions for retailers through longer-lasting food products present a compelling selling point. However, challenges such as potential greenwashing perceptions, logistical complexities in implementation, and the need for clear indications on compostable packaging disposal must be addressed. Additionally, obtaining **certification** for this smart food label could take some time. A central question will be to prove that this new label is indeed more performant than the current date marking.

4.2.4. Problem tree exercise SILL 8

Food waste generated at the retail level, unsuitable for donation or human consumption, poses significant environmental and logistical challenges, ultimately ending up in landfills. Food surplus prediction algorithms struggle due to various variables impacting retail, while short shelf life hinders timely donation. The decentralised nature of big retailers exacerbates logistical constraints.

Meanwhile, the production of biopolymers and cosmetics is currently largely petroleum-based. Alternative feedstocks are available but more expensive and not available at large scale.

A potential solution lies in valorising food waste by feeding it to microalgae, yielding sustainable compounds while addressing food waste issues. Governments can incentivise the use of sustainable alternatives through policies.

SILL 8 has developed a special container to store and dehydrate food waste at retail stores. The output of this process is used to feed micro-algae that are used for cosmetics or in biopolymer production.

Regional differences that emerged from the workshop

The types of food that goes to waste might differ from region to region. This means that the 'recipe' of what to put into the container could vary, but it would not have a major effect on the scalability of this solution.

4.2.6. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 8

The concept of using food waste to feed microalgae for various applications like bioplastics and cosmetics production is in its early stages. The cost is currently difficult to estimate, but it is expected to decrease as volume increases and optimal food residue streams are identified. Regardless of the exact costs, the workshop participants discussed the major advantages of using food waste to produce microalgae.

First of all, producing microalgae with food waste is much more sustainable than using fossil fuel-based inputs. The **environmental benefits** include a lower CO₂-footprint and reduced water usage compared to traditional practices. Microalgae's versatility in growth environments, such as saltwater and juice streams, presents opportunities for carbon credit generation. However, challenges persist, particularly concerning the energy-intensive production process, which currently relies on non-renewable energy sources. Transitioning to renewable energy is crucial to improve sustainability. Despite this, the versatility and adaptability of microalgae cultivation allow for the utilisation of various organic waste streams, ensuring long-term viability even as food waste from retail stores decreases.

Using food waste for cultivating microalgae also offers the advantage of producing a **biobased end-product**, aligning with the increasing demand for biobased products (both in food related but also cosmetics applications), such as pigments, antioxidants, and stabilisers. Moreover, niche ingredients or molecules can be directly extracted from the resulting powder, offering a cost-effective alternative to current production processes. The diversity of applications mirrors the diversity of available algae species and organic waste streams. Yet, despite the potential for various niche applications, these markets remain largely unexplored. Matching specific applications with suitable microalgae strains and optimising compounds to meet their requirements is crucial for advancing the solution and ensuring its widespread implementation. However, this process of matching applications to specific microalgae production presents a "chicken and egg" dilemma. Exploring applications across different sectors and bridging technical and commercial aspects can aid in finding suitable niches. Some considerations that should be kept in mind when screening the market are the odours and colours of the products generated by the algae and the fact that these organoleptic features of the end products can vary, depending on the waste stream that is used as a substrate for the algae.

Another important benefit is the fact that retailers will no longer have to throw away food; reducing food waste and saving disposal costs and taxes.

Practical considerations for feeding the dehydrator include the necessity to separate food from packaging, with any remaining packaging being processed as residue. Further testing is required to ensure the robustness of this process. Supermarket employees must possess the skills and knowledge to correctly operate the machine, including registering inputs and following recipes. Training these employees could be a service provided by the solution builders to support implementation. Biobased packaging could alleviate some issues and testing with such packaging (for example from SILL 2) is recommended.

Determining the optimal size and location of dehydrating machines is crucial for efficient **supply chain handling**. Options include centralising machines or deploying them at individual stores. While larger machines could cover multiple stores, this may require significant infrastructure changes. Alternatively, decentralised operations with waste management facilities on-site present logistical challenges, including long machine turnover time and insufficient powder distribution. Hence, the optimal logistical organisation of the powder, including mixing, packaging, and selling, needs further exploration.

The shelf life of the retail-level powder remains unknown. To ensure a balanced medium for microalgae growth, a mix of different waste streams following specific recipes is necessary. Automation through an app could help ensure consistency and alert operators of any issues with the mix.

Finally, the use of food waste to grow microalgae lacks a clear **legislative framework**, presenting both opportunities and challenges. The absence of regulations allows for flexible policy development but also poses uncertainties and risks regarding potential restrictive legislation. Certification is necessary for using microalgae in food applications or packaging to ensure food safety. However, obtaining certification for cosmetics presents additional challenges, such as meeting requirements for green ingredients and vegan certification, which may currently be unavailable.

4.3. Workshop on SILL 3, SILL 5 and SILL 6

4.3.1. General workshop information

A total of 38 participants joined the SILL 3, SILL 5 and SILL 6 workshop. These included SILL partners, tomato processors, meat processors, project partners, policy makers of the Andalusian government responsible for agriculture and fisheries, technology providers, universities, agricultural research and training institutes and food research and development agencies. The workshop took place in Motril, Spain on the 24th and 25th of October 2023.

4.3.2. Problem tree exercise SILL 3

The issue of overproduction of tomatoes is multifaceted, stemming from various factors. Supply chain disruptions due to cheaper imports, income fluctuations, and overproduction for contractual obligations, to name a few. Environmental factors such as unpredictable weather and disease outbreaks further contribute to yield variability. Marketing the overproduced or substandard tomatoes is very challenging. Surplus tomatoes are often wasted or underutilised, despite potential value in alternative uses like composting or biogas production. This is due to organisational factors, including inadequate data availability, limited automation hindering optimal planning and resource utilisation. Additionally, the lack of storage and processing infrastructure leads to late identification of substandard tomatoes.

The introduction of the SILL 3 **digital supply prediction tool** offers promise in addressing these challenges. By providing farmers with improved harvest prediction capabilities, the tool enables early identification of substandard tomatoes, optimising resource utilisation and reducing production costs. Additionally, the information provided by the system enables enhanced communication with supply chain partners.

Regional differences that emerged from the workshop

- Different light conditions in Lithuania versus Spain or Italy, meaning that the model needs to be adapted/re-trained.
- Different types of tomatoes require different calibration. This is possible but requires additional effort every time a different variety (new to the system) is produced. Regions where the same varieties are produced are more suited for the solution than regions where there is a lot of variation.

- When tomatoes are grown in controlled greenhouses, it is possible to adapt the heat and light to speed up or slow down the ripening process. In this way, the solution really allows demand-supply balancing. This effect is much more limited in countries that only use natural sunlight and warmth to grow tomatoes, like Spain.
- The average Farm size impacts to what extent this investment is feasible to make. In Lithuania, farms are usually larger than in Spain.
- This innovation will be easier to introduce in more technically advanced greenhouses, which is generally not the case in the Spanish tomato farming system.

4.3.3. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 3

The SILL 3 solution has the potential to offer numerous benefits - including cost savings and increased profits - to farmers, tomato distributors, and processing companies. By enabling early identification and removal of substandard tomatoes, the solution enhances overall quality and resource efficiency. However, the realisation of these advantages and the optimal implementation strategy depend heavily on the **prevailing market conditions in a regional farming system**. Originally tailored for the Lithuanian agricultural context, characterised by large temperature-controlled greenhouses for tomato cultivation and seamless Wi-Fi connectivity, the solution's implementation applicability faces distinct challenges in Andalusia, Spain. In this region, smaller-scale tomato producers rely on plastic greenhouses lacking advanced temperature regulation and with limited Wi-Fi access. Moreover, technical disparities between these contexts, such as varying light and moisture conditions, significantly affect data capture and processing. Thus, the applicability of the solution is much more straightforward in regions with similar farming systems as in Lithuania, while its applicability in regions with farming systems as in Spain has much lower potential – except when the solution gets adapted to fit the regional technological and food supply chain boundary conditions.

In addition to the early identification of suboptimal shapes, it is important to notice that the additional **benefits generated** from this tool – such as the ability to dynamically predict ripeness stages, or the possibility of also developing a pest management support tool – are different depending on the local food system context and accordingly the actors profiting from it. This holds important implications when it comes to scaling the solutions' precise design and scope of functions and its related marketing model: since different actors benefit from the solution depending on the context, there will also be different actors willing to **(co-) invest** in it.

In **Lithuania and regions with similar farming system contexts**, farmers would be the main benefactors from the solution as they stand to gain valuable insights into tomato ripening schedules, enabling precise temperature adjustments and ripening control. Given the narrow profit margins in the primary production sector, any tool that optimises workflow and reduces costs is welcomed. Yet, it remains to be proven if farmers will in fact gain time with this solution. Automation potential, such as replacing manual camera-trolley operation with automated systems, promises increased operational efficiency, particularly beneficial in case a farming sector faces labour shortages. Hence, for the sake of scaling SILL 3 solution in these types of regions, such optimisations of the solution should be identified (driven by the needs) and the solution should be developed accordingly. Further, if a region should be characterised by a general resistance among farmers to technological innovations, their attitude towards this solution should be addressed by demonstrating the benefits to them, which can be done e.g. via farmers advisory organizations, by sharing success stories from early adopters.

In **Spain and regions with similar farming system contexts**, tomato processors supported by farmers co-operatives rather than individual farmers themselves would benefit from the tool as it can facilitate processing planning and yield estimations. Here, implementing this solution necessitates centralised data collection, marking the initial step towards agricultural digitisation — a goal endorsed by the Spanish government, primarily focusing on digital bookkeeping. Here, government incentives promoting agricultural digitalisation can leverage the adoption of the tool.

Generally, scaling the solution warrants attention to **data privacy** since many pictures are taken of the tomatoes and anyone present in the greenhouse at that moment. This requires adequate GDPR compliance protocols. It also raises the question of who owns this data and if all the data may be used to train the model.

Furthermore, expanding its applicability to **different tomato varieties and other crops** demands thorough model training and recalibration, contingent upon market demands. Enhancements like integrating climate sensors, aligning with existing decision support tools or making a drone could bolster the solution's appeal and uptake.

4.3.4. Problem tree exercise SILL 5

Currently, the process of **identifying substandard or unattractive tomatoes is labour-intensive and time-consuming**. These inferior tomatoes often get mixed with higher quality ones, leading to batch rejections, wastage, lack of data, and transportation of tomatoes with shorter shelf lives to distant locations. Additionally, verifying the organic status of tomatoes involves lengthy and costly procedures. The underlying causes of these issues include a lack of automation, difficulty in manually identifying visually unappealing produce, subjectivity in quality assessment leading to inconsistencies across individuals, and the inability to accurately predict the quantity of tomatoes destined for processing.

To address these challenges, an **automated sorting platform** has been developed in SILL 5. This platform offers a rapid and non-destructive method for assessing sugar content and shelf life of tomatoes. Furthermore, it enables faster, albeit still destructive, verification of organic versus non-organic tomatoes. Unlike traditional methods requiring laboratory analysis and a day's wait for results, this platform conducts assessments on-site, eliminating delays. Consequently, substandard tomatoes can be promptly repurposed for processing into products like gazpacho or salmorejo.

This innovative solution not only streamlines quality control processes but also **reduces waste and enhances efficiency** throughout the tomato supply chain. By automating tasks and providing timely insights, it helps farmers and retailers to optimise their operations, minimise losses, and deliver fresher, higher-quality produce to consumers. Moreover, the platform's ability to quickly differentiate organic and non-organic tomatoes facilitates compliance with regulations and market demands, further bolstering the industry's sustainability and competitiveness.

Regional differences that emerged from the workshop

The main regional difference is related to where in the supply chain the machine is best placed. In the Spanish context, with several smaller farmers and one central processing company, the latter is the logical place. In the Lithuanian context, it would make more sense to position it at the greenhouse. (see SILL 3 for more context).

4.3.5. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 5

When identifying tomatoes with shorter shelf lives earlier in the process, they can be **valorised** more easily. Initially, the tomatoes are attempted to be sold to nearby customers; if feasible, they are reprocessed into other products. These alternative products could be marketed as made from "ugly" or substandard produce. Nowadays, there's a growing consumer acceptance of such products, provided they remain nutritious and tasty. This not only contributes to reduced food waste but also saves disposal costs.

Overall, this solution has the potential to foster **trust** among supply chain partners and improve operational and commercial planning **efficiency**. Currently, tomato control is manual and susceptible to errors. Automation ensures every tomato undergoes thorough examination, considering not just colour but also sugar content, a critical quality parameter. Although firmness cannot be controlled with this solution, the benefits are significant. However, realising these benefits requires clear communication, marketing efforts, and monitoring through KPIs. Quantifying the benefits in this specific use case could inspire others to adopt the same solution. An added benefit is that this way of working would increase food traceability.

Implementing this solution necessitates **operational changes**. Trained operators are required to operate and maintain the platform, potentially creating new job opportunities in rural areas. Adoption of the technology also demands process line adjustments, such as modifying the product line to accommodate the platform's multiple exits. Proper training is essential, as the imaging technique requires tomatoes to be entered correctly into the machine.

Building **worker trust** in the machine may pose a challenge, particularly in convincing them to embrace new ways of working and accept new technology. While this may lead to job losses for unskilled workers, it creates opportunities for educated workers.

The initial **investment cost** is high due to the need for training the module for each tomato variety. However, the data gathered through implementation holds significant value for further model training. Agreements on data collection and ownership are crucial, with potential for commercialisation of datasets by companies using the model. Currently, data sharing options are limited, with intellectual property belonging to Multiscan.

Transferring the solution to different varieties requires building and validating databases for each variety. Initial focus should be on similar tomato varieties. The

machine's applicability extends to other fruits such as potatoes, blueberries, nuts, olives, citrus, peaches, and avocados, with the cost of training models for new varieties determining scalability. Improvements in speed, such as increasing the number of cameras, could be necessary. Different wavelengths allow classification of various parameters, though current solutions utilise only a limited range. Finding the right wavelength for critical parameters is crucial, considering factors like cost and effectiveness.

4.3.6. Problem tree exercise SILL 6

Current **quality and process controls in poultry production** are limited, often relying on subjective judgments from operators and periodic lab sampling. Non-conformities and unexpected events result in food waste and inefficient resource utilisation, impacting both consumption and manufacturing levels in the meat sector. Inefficiencies in production include material and consumable losses, time wastage, staff effort, and the need for reworks. Difficulties in production control affect planning and potential optimisations, leading to client claims and brand damage in case of problems. Deficiencies in current controls include human decision-making, lack of expertise, subjective tests, and delays in lab analysis. Moreover, the heterogeneity of food and old processing equipment pose challenges for quality control automation.

To overcome these challenges, there is a need for tools that are simple for non-experts to use, increasing the frequency or ideally enabling continuous quality and process control. Proactive, data-driven decision-making approaches are crucial. A solution lies in developing new **portable digital devices**, based on Near Infrared (NIR) technology, coupled with automated software. These tools would facilitate faster and more continuous quality and process controls at various production points, enabling quicker issue mitigation. Ultimately, this approach not only reduces food waste but also promotes more efficient resource utilisation in poultry production.

4.3.7. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 6

For every new tool that is implemented, it is important to balance the benefits it brings versus the investment cost. For the SILL 6 solution, the **internal and operational benefits** include the ability to detect problems faster, optimise logistics, and reprocess products instead of wasting them. The tools save time and enhance operational efficiency by facilitating quicker rework. However, it is important to note that these solutions cannot replace official/reference methods but serve as pre-analysis tools. While they indicate products for sampling, legally required tests still

need to be conducted, meaning there is no reduction in waiting time for official results nor an increase in shelf life. Another advantage is the solution's **portability**, allowing for ease of use at different points along the production line. This adaptability enhances flexibility and usability. However, a drawback is that the solution cannot easily be implemented in the automated production line.

The solution enables real-time testing of a high number of samples or entire batches, reducing the number of complaints and allowing immediate action to halt or recall problematic batches before they reach consumers. This proactive approach enhances **food safety and quality** and mitigates risks associated with delayed testing results. This increases consumer confidence in food safety. This benefit could be marketed in a partnership with NIR device producers to showcase the solution's effectiveness, enhancing competitiveness and demonstrating good practices.

Maintenance service is a critical aspect of implementing this solution, necessitating strategic partnerships with hardware and other key providers. Currently the model is tailored for specific devices, making adaptation to other hardware complex. Collaboration with different hardware companies is possible but requires coordination. Ultimately, the final client decides which hardware to use, emphasising the need for commercial partnerships with hardware providers. These partnerships involve integrating the model into their devices and providing ongoing support in case of faults, highlighting the importance of fostering strong relationships with hardware providers to ensure successful implementation.

Worker **satisfaction and motivation** can increase as these tools help avoid situations where their efforts lead to product discard due to deviations. However, training is necessary to operate these devices effectively. Currently, the workers only perform the scanning, and the interpretation is done by the quality manager. Resistance to adopting new technology may arise due to fears of job loss, necessitating change management strategies to address concerns and encourage adoption.

The solution's **transferability and scalability** depend on several factors. Since it is a mobile device it can be applied in other production lines or product types. Operational considerations include the need for recalibration when using the device on different food products or changing parameters like packaging material or measurement distance. Sensitivity limitations and interference from factors like temperature and packaging materials pose challenges, necessitating calibration under conditions matching actual use. The solution's applicability varies depending on product composition and the technology's detection limits. Product composition refers to the fact that the sensor measure at the surface, which is sufficient for homogenous products like minced meat but would not work for e.g. pork chops.

While portable sensors offer cost-effectiveness for salt measurement, and allow testing several parameters simultaneously, they are not sensitive enough to detect very low levels of nitrites as mandated by current legislation.

Data availability and collection are crucial for creating models in this solution. However, questions arise regarding **data governance and ownership**. Commercial players typically collect vast amounts of data through their devices. The ownership of this data is a significant consideration. Given the extensive data requirements for model creation, determining ownership becomes paramount. Clarifying who owns the collected data is essential for addressing concerns regarding privacy, control, and potential commercial exploitation.

4.4. Workshop on SILL 4 and SILL 7

4.4.1. General workshop information

A total of 33 participants joined the SILL 4 and SILL 7 workshop. These included all SILL 4 partners, the lead partners of SILL 7, policy representatives from the Department of agriculture & fisheries of the Flemish government, representatives of one of the main Belgian fruit and vegetable auction, Dutch food banks, the international food bank federation, social entrepreneurs working with food surpluses, partners from work packages 6, 7 and 8.

4.4.2. Problem tree exercise SILL 4

The problem addressed by SILL 4 revolves around the issue of **pre-consumer fruit and vegetable losses**, characterised by diverse and volatile factors. These include farmers leaving food unharvested due to factors such as bad pricing, volatile production, not meeting retailers' quality standards, and the absence of contracts for produce that render harvest and logistics costs higher than profits. Auctions often redirect unsold fruit to bioenergy and feedstock production due to logistical challenges and the lack of processing capacity. Legal obligations regarding donations and liability concerns regarding food safety further complicate the issue. Despite efforts by food banks, logistical challenges and economic viability hinder effective processing and redistribution. The proposed solution, SILL 4, introduces a **mobile fruit and vegetable processing installation**. Its versatility allows to process smaller batches of varying surplus fruit and vegetable feedstocks into high quality fruit juices

or purees. These products could be commercialised as 'rescued and local produce' or they could be donated to food banks.

4.4.3. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 4

Commercialise rescued fruit and vegetables

The commercial route could benefit from the fact that there is a **niche customer segment** like the 'food waste warriors', highlighting an increasing interest in products made from leftovers. Strategic placement of processing units in regions abundant with fruit and vegetable producers would be pivotal, potentially optimising operations and market accessibility. Additionally, **empowering farmers** to process surplus production directly for direct sales offers a viable alternative to conventional auction systems, which often result in unsold produce redirected to **bioenergy and feedstock** production due to logistical challenges and lack of processing capacity. Moreover, emphasising local production as a unique selling point can attract consumers willing to pay premiums for genuinely local produce.

The **open factory line** was identified as a good way to involve consumers and pupils in food processing in general. As public consciousness around these issues grows, new business models and policy actions are increasingly being driven by societal pressure and demand for sustainable practices.

Flexible processing of surplus food to stimulate donations

When exploring the route of donating the end products, there are some **legal and legislative challenges** that need to be considered. Varied approaches across EU countries to liability, donations, and food safety regulations necessitate nuanced strategies for effective food waste reduction efforts. Legislative frameworks governing food processing, safety, and donations add layers of complexity, demanding careful consideration and adaptation to local contexts.

Taking food out of the market is a very effective tool to reduce FLW and tackle hunger. However, this is only allowed in countries that have this strategy to reduce FLW incorporated in their Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) strategic plan. There are of course regulations in place to allow authorities to verify whether the food that is taken out of the market is indeed donated and not flowing back to the commercial circuit. This is clearly described for fruits and vegetables that are donated, but it becomes a bit more complicated when these fruits and vegetables are transformed

into juices and then donated. How much juice or puree we can expect from 1 kg of inputs depends on the processing technique used, the type of inputs and various other aspects. Hence, one of the aims of SILL 4 is to support policy makers in gathering the necessary information to be able to develop this kind of legislation. This will support scaling the solution to other countries.

An interesting **case in Spain** was mentioned where the auctions donate fruit and vegetables to the food bank, the food bank has it processed by an external party which is in turn paid in kind with part of the produce. There is EU legislation that makes this possible (Directive 2022/126), but this is not yet translated into local legislation in all EU countries. To be able to translate this into national legislation, Member States first need to include 'taking produce out of the market' in their CAP strategic plan.

Participants also mentioned that **food safety and traceability regulations** for donated food represent a cost for food banks and donors. There is a good IT system in place at the food banks (FoodIT), but it is only implemented for dry food and not (always) for fresh food. Supporting food banks to develop a similar system for fresh food would enable the interactions and logistical flows to be arranged when collaborating with donors in general and the mobile unit in particular.

Although the main focus of this SILL is developing the mobile processing unit, indirectly this means **stimulating more donations to food banks**. The more food is being donated to food banks which cannot be donated on time, the more innovative ways of processing, preserving and redistributing this food will take off. A hurdle that was discussed in this regard is the handling costs incurred by auctions when re-packing pallets into smaller crates. This is necessary to allow authorities to perform controls and auctions can request financial compensation for this. However, they are not always equipped in terms of personnel to perform these actions. This hurdle needs to be overcome in order to scale the SILL 4 solution.

There is another interesting opportunity to stimulate reprocessing surplus food. In the CAP strategic plan, auctions now have the option to dedicate some EU money to research & innovation on circularity. This could stimulate the auctions to invest in a processing line for example.

Both pathways to reach impact will require new partnerships to be formed, ideally between existing stakeholders in the food surplus and food redistribution charities. Participants pointed out that there is a **lack of trust** between industry stakeholders and social enterprises. This is blocking effective collaboration.

The **mobility of the unit** was considered less important and even as a hurdle, at least in the region of Flanders. Setting up the container in a new place generates setup costs and complicates the operations. A strategically located processing unit, that is flexible in terms of processing capabilities, was considered more important.

From a technological point of view, some issues were raised. The unit uses **Pulsed Electric Fields** as a conservation technique. This brings benefits from a product quality point of view – the food retains more of its original nutritional value. However, the shelf life is 4 to 6 weeks compared to a year or more when using pasteurisation as a conservation technique. The disadvantage of the shorter shelf life does not outweigh the food quality advantage according to the participants. This motivated the SILL to replace the PEF technique by traditional sterilisation.

4.4.4. Problem Tree exercise SILL 7

Despite the prevalence of **food waste in retail stores**, the issue of **food insecurity** continues to worsen, with food banks experiencing shortages and limitations. Root causes contributing to this discrepancy include limited food bank operating hours, absence of legislation prohibiting disposal of edible food, lack of financial incentives for donation, and inconsistencies in donation quantities and types. Additionally, perishable items pose challenges for donation due to their short shelf life and risk aversion in food safety concerns. The mismatch between food bank needs and donations arises from regional disparities, logistical constraints, and specific dietary requirements not always being met. GDPR regulations further complicate efforts by prohibiting the registration of certain food preferences.

SILL 7 aims to address these challenges by identifying bottlenecks and proposing solutions in a comprehensive **donation handbook**. Additionally, a **forecasting tool** will facilitate communication of food bank needs, while a **donation tool** will streamline the donation process for retailers. These initiatives aim to integrate food banks into the supply chain and enhance their operational efficiency, ultimately mitigating food waste and alleviating food insecurity.

Regional differences that emerged from the workshop

- Scale up and application of the SILL7 solution may be particularly interesting in regions where donation amounts tend to diminish; to maximise limited resources.
- Differences in supply chain logistics across regions impact the replicability of the tool, which makes the application of the model in different contexts more difficult.
- No uniformity across countries in managing food poverty. Each country has different needs and different behavioural habits and cultural differences.

4.4.5. Critical success factors for scaling SILL 7

SILL 7's solution focuses on enhancing the **internal operations of food banks** to optimise the utilisation of available donated food. Effective communication regarding donation drop-off times is highlighted as crucial for donors. Moreover, the method of distributing food to those in need is under reconsideration, debating between pre-filled boxes and a supermarket-style selection process. The SILL 7 initiative includes the development of a dashboard and model to assist food banks in making **strategic investment decisions**. These decisions involve determining whether to allocate resources towards transport, freezer capacity, or general storage, considering the limited availability of volunteers. Efficiency in volunteer utilisation is paramount, and the tools provided by SILL 7 offer significant potential for scalability. Food banks indicated that they also need a system to manage the content of their freezer more effectively.

Collaboration between donating companies and food banks is deemed advantageous, with a particular focus on improving the timing of donations to facilitate prompt redistribution. Although guidelines exist for this purpose, they are not widely known, representing an opportunity for improvement. This is especially important to improve the data sharing between food banks and donators. The volatility in the amount of donations is very high, swinging from massive oversupply to shortages. Only through data sharing we could move to better forecasting these peaks and adapting the organisation towards it. At present, we do not have access to retailers' inventory data for these purposes. SILL 7 is collaborating with a retailer to explore the possibilities of sharing inventory data for these purposes.

Efficient donation practices **benefit retailers** by reducing disposal costs and maintaining the freshness of displayed food. Donating food instead of selling it at a discount reduces retailers' income, but this could be compensated by selling more of the fresher produce. Participants in the workshop have suggested tracking and

comparing the amount of food waste generated by different retailers to incentivise waste reduction efforts.

The implementation of **legal and policy best practices**, exemplified by Portugal's approach, could be expanded. In Portugal, retailers receive financial incentives for donations but must register these donations to access the benefits. This system results in increased donations and provides valuable data on how much food is donated. This could be a huge opportunity to incentivise access to data on food surpluses. Additionally, a simulation model is being developed to forecast the potential impact of tax regulations, although it operates based on certain assumptions.

5. Conclusion: innovation scale-up success factors and incentives

For the ZeroW SILLs to achieve their goal of significantly reducing food loss and waste (FLW), it is crucial that they can be implemented at large scale or replicated in different European regions. To support this process, we conducted stakeholder workshops for each of the SILLs and tried to unravel the main barriers and enablers they face in this process of reaching impact. We decided not to focus on unravelling differences in scaling success factors for different EU regions but rather we focused on each SILL individually. This approach allowed us to generate context specific and actionable insights.

Many different stakeholders shared their view on our nine living labs and the results are detailed in this report D6.1. The next step is to concentrate on the main barriers for each of the SILLs and develop adequate capacity building activities to overcome these. This will be the subject of T6.2 and D6.2. The exact focus of each capacity building activity will be discussed in WP6 and with the relevant SILL partners, but the main conclusions from the stakeholder workshops (summarized hereafter per SILL) provide a starting point.

SILL 1 develops a supply chain overarching data sharing platform, pivotal to map FLW. Achieving this is however very challenging because different supply chain actors across industries need to work together and interact with policy makers at different levels. This requires a lot of coordination but also a different mindset towards sharing data. Supporting SILL 1 in fostering the right mindset will help pave the way for standardised data collection and sharing in the long run.

SILL 9 partners are already in this mindset and provide an excellent example of the potential of having such a dataset available. They currently use a (limited) dataset on consumer FLW and data on CO₂-emissions of food products to develop a label and a menu planning app that focuses on FLW. Apart from having the right input data, it is also important to convince consumers to use the app and the label to guide their consumption behaviour. This is strongly linked to trust and motivation of the users and could be a very relevant capacity building pathway.

The smart and compostable packaging developed in **SILL 2** will show the actual freshness of a food product and thus avoid food waste due to inaccurate date markings. The main challenge here is offsetting the additional cost of this innovative packaging. While there are many advantages throughout the supply chain, quantifying them and communicating about them is crucial to convince stakeholders. A second route for upscaling this solution is the enforcement of compostable

packaging. Once this packaging is implemented, it will also be important to guide this change of date marking on the consumers' side.

The main barrier for upscaling the food waste-based feedstock for micro algae of **SILL 8** is finding the right market application. There are many known and unknown options, and it is difficult to decide which application has the most potential. Extensive networking and further discussions with industry players could help to clarify this and further develop this solution.

For the tomato quality and ripeness scanning device of **SILL 3**, we have identified the type of greenhouses where this solution has the most potential: large scale greenhouses with temperature control options. This will help the direction of scaling considerably. Also, the insight that farmers want a package solution that offers not only the software but also the hardware and maybe even link it with other solutions like pest management was an important feedback from the workshop participants. Finally, the opportunity of linking this solution to the overall demand from governments to digitise farming could enable further implementation.

Scaling the **SILL 5 and SILL 6** solutions should start by implementation at the SILL partners and measuring the impact it has on efficiency and food waste reduction. In SILL 5, the tomato sorting device will help identify the shorter shelf life and lower quality tomatoes and redirect them towards processing facilities. In SILL 6, the mobile and online detection of salt and nitrite levels in poultry products will prevent quality issues later on in the process and the food waste that results from this. These success stories will be a catalysator for further implementation in other companies and on similar food products.

The main enablers for scaling the flexible food processing unit of **SILL 4** lies in the policy domain. Extending the regulations for taking food out of the market for donation to include processing of this food before donating it, is paramount to further develop this solution.

The food donation tool and handbook together with the forecasting tool from **SILL 7** are aimed at increasing supply chain collaboration to reduce FLW. The main challenge is informing stakeholders of the tools that are available and convincing them of their benefits. This can be done by showcasing successful implementations of early adopters.

Despite the great variety across FLW solutions developed in the SILLs in terms of scope and context and our aim to work on a SILL by SILL basis (e.g., FLW problem they are addressing, value chain stages they are covering, etc.), some recurring success factors for the development of FLW solutions can be identified:

- **Economic feasibility and viable business models.** Many SILLs have the business and value chain dimensions either identified as their bottleneck dimension or as a dimension where the initial level is rather low on the

maturity ladder. For SILLs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 8, the business model and value chain implementation is still unclear. For SILLs 7 and 9, it is not so much about identifying what business model would fit, rather there is no clear incentive to develop the business model due to a lack of identified target users who are willing to invest in the scale-up of the tools. Every SILL is searching for the best possible, profitable business model for scale-up. Indeed, many innovative solutions must find a way to balance the investment costs and the created value or benefits provided by their solution and finding suitable business models and aligning operational costs with implementation costs is widely seen as a prerequisite for adoption. The success of a certain business model may largely depend on context factors such as supply chain conditions and regional economic differences, as was showed by the SILL4 case.

- **User-friendliness and added value for end users.** For SILL 1's data platform, user-friendliness with customizable interfaces is crucial for sustained usage. The success of the apps from SILL 9 will depend on the practical usability and lay-out of the interface in order to keep consumers motivated to use it. In SILL 2, the label must be easy to interpret but also accepted and trusted by all end users. SILLs 5 and 6 emphasize the need for solutions that are easy to use for non-experts, such as factory workers.
- **Validation and demonstration of usefulness and benefits.** Related to the need for establishing user-friendliness and added value for end users, a common critical success factor for FLW solutions concerns a thorough validation of the usability and ease of use among end users. For many tools, it is important to validate their usefulness and benefits with end users. SILL 1 plans to test an automated data collection process in Slovenia as a use case. Sharing success stories and demonstrating benefits can help promote adoption. For SILL 5 and SILL 6, implementation by their own partners and impact measurement are seen as starting points for broader roll-out. Demonstrating the added value for farmers is highlighted as important by SILL 3.
- **Technological infrastructure and data governance.** For several SILLs, including SILL 1, SILL 5, SILL 6, SILL7, and SILL 9, datasets form a crucial part of the solution. Setting up technological infrastructures and data governance models to ensure sustainable engagement and capabilities of data owners and recipients is a recurring success factor. Questions about data ownership and management must be addressed in FLW solutions where data sharing is part of the solution.
- **Policy support and regulation.** Legislation at EU or regional level influences the scalability of the solutions. For SILL 4 and SILL 8, changes in specific policy domains are identified as a crucial prerequisite for scale-up. For example, for SILL 4, Flemish regulation prevents processing of fruit and vegetables that are withdrawn from the market, thus making it impossible to launch the mobile food processor in a food donation context. For SILL 2, legal measures such as

mandating compostable packaging could stimulate adoption by food packagers and food processing companies. Obviously, each FLW solution must be carefully analysed (in a case-by-case manner) to check for regional differences in the policy mix that influence transferability and potential for scale-up.

- **Collaboration and stakeholder engagement.** For many solutions, collaboration among actors in the food chain is essential. For example, SILL 1 works with local and national governments; SILL 4 highlights the importance of interaction with food banks, auctions, retailers, and policymakers, and sees forming new partnerships as critical; SILL7 connects actors generating food surplus with food banks and charity organisations. Involving relevant stakeholders from an early stage already is widely regarded as a means to improve broad applicability and scalability of solutions.
- **Adaptation to regional contexts.** Differences between EU regions—such as in digitalization (SILL 1), consumption habits (SILL 9), waste legislation (SILL 2), growing conditions (SILL 3), and food bank logistics (SILL 7)—underline the need to adapt solutions to specific regional contexts for successful scale-up.

These shared success factors show that developing effective measures to reduce food waste is a complex and multifaceted process that goes beyond technological innovation. It requires attention to economic viability, user acceptance, data infrastructure, policy support, collaboration, regional adaptation, and demonstrating concrete benefits.

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Annex I: Workshop invitation template

e-mail subject: **Invitation to workshop 'How to foster scale-up of innovative solutions to food waste problems'**

Dear [contact],

I would like to invite you to the interactive workshop 'How to foster scale-up of innovative solutions to food waste problems' on [date]. The workshop takes place in [location].

This workshop is organised as a part of the European HE project [ZeroW](#), wherein nine concrete and promising solutions for significantly reducing food losses and waste (FLW) are developed in nine respective SILLs (Systemic Innovation Living Labs). In building these solutions, we are keen to involve different actors who have interest in making food systems more sustainable.

Why are you invited to this workshop?

In order to ensure that the innovations we develop in ZeroW are effective and can mature towards successful scaling, we are organising stakeholder workshops wherein two pilot projects will be presented to a selected group of external stakeholders. We have carefully selected a group of stakeholders with the right expertise to make this workshop relevant for both you and for the project. We recognise the expertise and significant work done by [Name of Entity] in the field of [area of expertise], and believe that your participation would be extremely valuable to enrich the discussions and contribute with relevant insights. We will ask you to provide input on our project based on your expertise. You will be able to discover two innovative FLW solutions and expand your network. Below this e-mail you can find more details on the two innovations that will be discussed.

What will we do during the workshop?

The aim of this workshop is to determine which concrete actions and strategies can increase the scale-up potential of these systemic solutions to FLW. For this, we will use a systemic approach to share the progress of each pilot project, looking at the innovation through different lenses. We will zoom in on the critical innovation dimensions and identify actions and factors that could foster or hamper the scaling of the innovation.

We would be delighted to have your presence and contribution to make the workshop a productive, inspiring and enriching event. Participation in the workshop is free of charge. We kindly request that you communicate your interest in participating by

replying to this e-mail before **[defined schedule]**. If there is any representative or expert from **[Entity Name]** whom you recommend for participation, please provide us with their contact information so that we can extend the invitation to them directly.

If you have any questions or need further information, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Looking forward to hearing your response.

Kind regards,

[your name and organisation]

Mobile food processing unit

Can we avoid the unpredictable fruit and vegetable surpluses with a mobile and flexible food processing unit using an 'as a service' business model?

Efficient food bank networks

Can we improve the matching of supply and demand at the food bank in order to reduce food waste while still addressing the major issue of food insecurity?

Annex II: script (playbook) for the workshops

Workshop agenda

(this can be adjusted based on specific contexts/needs per workshop)

Table 5 Template agenda for workshops

Time	Topic	Duration
8h30 - 9h00	Welcome & coffee	30 min
9h00 - 9h10	Introduction & aim of the day (Lisa/Isabeau)	10 min
9h10 - 9h30	Introduce participants (tour de table or icebreaker)	20 min
9h30 - 10h15	Present SILLA (problem, technical solution, Status & ambition using SIRL + choose 2 dimensions)	45 min
10h15 - 10h45	Demo (if possible)	30 min
10h45 - 11h00	Coffee	15 min
11:00 - 12h00	Division in 2 groups: per dimension, list actions/events/trends that are conducive for or obstacle to the development of the solution/making progress on SIRL ladder 15 min individual 30 min discussion 15 min prioritise + match green & red	60 min
12h00 - 12h30	Plenary discussion on how to overcome threats/obstacles or foster opportunities	30 min
12h30 - 13h30	Lunch	60 min
13h30 - 14h15	Present SILLB (problem, technical solution, Status & ambition using SIRL + choose 2 dimensions)	45 min
14h15 - 14h45	Demo	30 min
14h45 - 15h00	Coffee	15 min
15h00 - 16h00	Division in 2 groups: per dimension, list actions/events/trends that are conducive for or obstacle to the development of the solution/making	60 min

	progress on SIRT ladder 15 min individual 30 min discussion 15 min prioritise + match green & red	
16h00 – 16h30	Plenary discussion on how to overcome threats/ obstacles or foster opportunities +closing	30 min
16h30 – 17h30	Networking reception (optional)	60 min

Workshop materials

- Flipchart (2x)
- Pencils (enough for all participants)
- Sticky notes (enough to give a pile to each participant)
- Recording devices (3 or more)
- Beamer, screen, adaptors for laptops, pointer
- SIRT ppt to present problem, solution, and status & ambition (using SIRT)
- Mural board in case of online workshop

Annex III: SIRL Radars

Annex IV: Questionnaire for SILLs in preparing stakeholder workshops

Question	Answer options
Is your SILL suitable for scaling up?	
	Yes
	No
	Yes, but...
Is it possible to simplify the solution you are developing or scale-up parts of it?	
	Yes
	No, it is not possible to simplify or scale up only parts of the solution
	Yes, but...
On a scale from 1 to 7, to what extent will you have a working business model at the end of the ZeroW project?	
	1 : Will not be generating profits
	7: We will generate profit and be able to cover all operational costs with these profits
What kind of scaling up do you envision? *	
	Replication: the SILL's technology or model is implemented elsewhere
	Expanding: the scope of the SILLs' operations is increased
	Collaborating: partnerships or networks are developed to spread the SILLs' results, methods
Are there partners/other stakeholders that you are already in contact with and whom should be present during the workshops? Where are they based?	
What kind of stakeholders do you want to be on the workshops? E.g., based on your SILL exercise.	
Which organisations are best suited to implement the SILL on a scaled-up basis or serve as partners in implementing the model? **	
In which NUTS2 region are you currently situated with developing/implementing your solution?	

Are there certain European regions that would be more suitable for scaling? If so, which ones and why?	
What would scaling up look like if it were successful? ***	Note: be as specific as possible and think broadly (using the SIRL!) Ensure a broad interpretation beyond the core (technical) solution
Is the funding that is required for scaling available? ****	
	No
	Yes
	Not yet, but we are working on it
When would you like to start the scaling up process? How long do you envision the total process to take?	
Discuss possible formats to present the SILL Do you have any material (e.g., videos, website, folders, leaflets, Youtube channel, social media, ppt, short act, ...) that could be used for presenting your systemic innovation to stakeholders? So that these stakeholders have the right type of knowledge about your solution, and they can assess its potential and contribute to the matchmaking.	
	Yes, we have...
	No
Is your organisation able to host a local workshop? We will need a meeting room for +/- 25 persons	
	Yes, we are located in....
	No
Is there another SILLs' workshop that you would like to attend because you feel you can contribute to their scaling?	
Are there other SILL members or ZeroW partners whom you would like to attend your workshop because you feel they can contribute to your scaling?	

Annex V: Adapted agenda for online stakeholder workshop

9.15 - 9.45	Welcome and introduction to the workshop and participants
9.45 - 10.15	Discover pilot 1: How can an open data-driven platform help in reducing food loss and waste?
10.15 - 10.55	Identify trends that foster or hamper the development of an open data platform for collecting food loss and waste data
10.55 - 11.15	Coffee break
11.15 - 11.45	Discover Pilot 9: How can meal boxes, labels, recipes and other digital solutions help consumers in making 'better' food choices?
11.45 -12.25	Identify trends that foster or hamper the digital solutions to support consumers in their food choices
12.25 - 12.40	Closing